

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN:

Roles and responsibilities: Primary responsibility for implementing and monitoring this data management plan will be held by the Co-PI, Rachel Rosenbaum. She will design and implement interview, fieldnote, and audio/visual data collection protocols and will conduct all data analysis. The PI, Brian Silverstein, will oversee this research and provide guidance on data collection and analysis protocols and dissemination of findings. The Co-PI will be responsible for overall project management and ensuring that data management observes all Internal Review Board guidelines for Human Subject Protection. Adherence to this data management plan will be demonstrated in future reporting to the Co-PI's department, the School of Anthropology at the University of Arizona (UA), where doctoral students are evaluated on the ethics, monitoring of their data, and human subject protection prior to, during, and after their doctoral research. She will disseminate the information from the collected data through diverse publications and public presentations. There will be no transference of the data management to another PI or Co-PI, and all management will remain with the Co-PI, Rachel Rosenbaum.

Data types and format: All data will only be collected with participant permission. This research will collect textual, audio, and visual data. Textual data will be in the form of fieldnotes, interview notes from ethnographic interviews and participant observation, complete interview transcriptions, publicly available text media (i.e. journal articles and government documents), social media posts shared with permission, and documents from research collaborators shared with the Co-PI. Digital textual data will be stored in Microsoft Word, PDF, and Excel file formats. Audio data will be in the form of recorded interviews and WhatsApp voice messages. Interviews will be recorded using a Zoom audio recorder. Audio files will be promptly moved from the audio recorder to the Co-PI's laptop and stored in .mp3 file format. WhatsApp voice messages will be downloaded from the desktop app on the Co-PI's computer and stored in .mp3 file format. Visual data will be in the form of photographs of repair practices and the urban environment taken with the Co-PI's camera/phone, photos and videos taken by research participants of their practices or relevant information and sent to the Co-PI, and publicly available media or media shared directly with the Co-PI (such as videos and social media photos). Photos taken by the Co-PI will be moved from the camera to the Co-PI's laptop and stored as .jpg files. Any identifiable photos will not be shared unless with expressed permission from all in the photos. Other visual data will be stored as .jpg or .mov files on the Co-PI's laptop. Data analysis will be processed with NVivo qualitative software. The Co-PI's MacBook laptop, external LaCie brand hard drive, and Box password protected cloud storage will store all data and data analysis.

Data management: Handwritten notes will be taken in notebooks that will be kept in a locked filing cabinet at the PI's office or home. These notes will be transcribed daily into qualitative data software for later analysis. Fieldnotes and interview notes will be transcribed into NVivo qualitative data software at the end of each day. Recorded interviews will be transcribed into NVivo within one week of being recorded. Audio files will be moved from the audio recorder and saved as an .mp3 file on the Co-PI's laptop. The file name will be saved with a pseudonym only known by the Co-PI with the date of the interview. Visual data will be moved from the camera or phone of the Co-PI to her laptop and saved as a .jpg file. Data will be analyzed using NVivo qualitative software as outlined in the project description. All data and data analysis will be backed up from the Co-PI's laptop automatically to her password protected Box cloud storage (daily backups) and to an external LaCie brand hard drive (twice per week). This follows data management protocols that suggest all data is stored in at least 2 different locations. The laptop is password protected and, in case of theft, able to be erased remotely using Apple's "Find my Phone" feature. All files pertaining to this research will be password protected and encrypted. All information backed up to the external hard drive and Box will also be password protected with files requiring a passcode to be opened. Box, supplied by the University of Arizona, requires double verification protection – a password and a passcode texted to the Co-PI's personal mobile phone. These steps are taken to ensure maximum safety and protection of data. The Co-PI's laptop and hard drive will be securely stored at her office or home during research. Only the

Co-PI will have access to raw data and metadata. Research participants will be able to request access to any raw data that does not compromise confidentiality or anonymity of other participants.

Data Confidentiality and Protections: This research project will strictly follow the UA's Institutional Review Board Guidelines for Human Subjects data. Before any research or data collection begins the PI will obtain oral and/or written consent from participants. Following UA's IRB guidelines, written consent forms will be kept on file for six years in a secure location that only the PI and Co-PI will access. Participants' will be given a pseudonym and ID number after consenting to be a part of the research in a file that only the Co-PI will have access to and this file will adhere to the data and file security protocols above. This pseudonym and ID will be attached to files containing identifiable collected data such as interview recording files temporarily. Any such data will be transcribed within 3 weeks of being collected and the original files will then be deleted so that in the short and long-term the data will be low risk for being re-identified. Participants' identifying information will be removed from the metadata, databases, publications, and public presentations.

Policies and provisions for data re-use re-distribution: This research is of importance to ongoing rebuilding efforts in Beirut and therefore the findings from the data will be made available to various parties digitally. Relevant parties will be given access to particularly useful raw data, such as transcripts from interviews, databases of media files, or statistical data drawn from the findings, which does not harm any confidentiality or anonymity of research participants. For example, non-government institutions involved urban development policy and implementation as well as in-country research partners will be interested in the research findings and will be granted access to raw data and findings as approved by the Co-PI. These organizations will have to be vetted by the Co-PI to ensure that the purpose of use for data is in-line with the goals and aims of the research. Data use agreements may be drafted where necessary to specify the terms of use.

Data Dissemination: Data will be disseminated in a multiplatform fashion to guarantee both intellectual merit and broader impact. First, findings will be presented by the Co-PI at national conferences such as the American Anthropological Association and the Middle East Studies Association. To reach a global audience, findings will also be presented internationally through invited talks and conferences such as the annual conference by the Royal Anthropological Institute and local conferences in Lebanon run by NGOs and journals such as "Kohl". Second, findings will be published by the Co-PI in peer-reviewed journals such as *Cultural Anthropology*, *American Ethnology*, and *City and Society* within three years of completing the research. Third, findings will be summarized in a "white paper" report with actionable suggestions and ideas for urban development initiatives to be shared with local and international organizations, policy centers, and interested academics/practitioners such as those at Columbia University's "Post Conflict Cities Lab" and The American University of Beirut's "Issam Fares Institute for Public Policy and International Affairs." Fourth, the Co-PI will publish short articles in public facing platforms such as news media pieces and articles for well-trafficked sites such as Jadaliyya and Al-Monitor. The data that is supporting all of these activities will be made available in data repositories. This may include redacted passages of transcripts, Nvivo analysis snapshots, or quantitative data. I anticipate disseminating this data and documentation on the Open Anthropology Research Repository, ReliefWeb, and the AAA Data Registry Wiki.

Data Storage and Preservation of Access: All data will be stored in full compliance with the UA IRB on the Co-PI's personal laptop, external hard drive, and Box cloud storage. Even after transcription, all raw, identified data will be kept for future research purposes. Future access to data by people who are not the PI and Co-PI will be determined by the PI and Co-PI and will require IRB permission. Data will be kept for 10 years.